

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

EXPLORATION THE ESSENCE OF THE MYTHOLOGY AND ITS ROLE IN THE SCIENCE OF GEOLOGY

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Annotation: *The scientific look at of mythology is ruled through a paradigm that acknowledges mythology as having been considered as honest narrative records through beyond conventional cultures and but is considered fake or in any other case suspect through the present day scientists who look at mythology. Although really all scientists understand that myth become of important significance for conventional cultures, the try and elicit scientific motives for this significance has brought about many competing theories, few of which place an emphasis at the validity of myths as representing the fabricated from real determined historical events.*

Keywords: *myth, mythology, geology, paradigm, culture, disciplines.*

A modern study of myths is important part of many disciplines such as, anthropology, art history, classical literature, social sciences and humanities, including comparative religions, folklore, psychology and theology (Dandes 1984). Thousands of scholarly books and dozens of thousands of articles and dissertations are written about "myths" and the subject of their research. Its roots go back to the beginning of the myth and they revealed from human history and have got popularity from TV shows like Xena and Blockbuster movies such as Star Wars and the Lord of the circle which are still strong part of modern popular culture.

The most typical are myths, legends and folktales can be seen in the context of division oral prose or poetic story into three components that often overlap (e.g. Bascom 1965). Folktales are non-religious fictional stories they often teach practical lessons and draw morals, but they are intended to be entertaining. They are also non-historical, especially in that they are not tied to anything. We should not confuse folktales in the term "folklore", the latter is expression of folktales and other creative words (containing myths and legends) are learnt by folklorists' usage of literary and ethnographic folklore technique.

Geology and Mythology.

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As we have known, mythological research is extremely difficult and multifaceted topic and we've put a lot of effort to understand it. Many authors, since ancient times, have recognized the probable historical merit of mythology. Most of Greek mythology today it is known as a political and religious story. The destruction of the Troy described in Iliad, it was finally recognized as a genuine history in 1870. When Heinrich Schliemann dug the ruins Old Ilion. Moreover, among many other examples, The story of Theseus killing the Minotaur The palace of Knossos is generally considered to be one Cracked image of the last historic defeat Minoan civilization in the Aegean Sea (c. 1400 BC).

An example that can help explain the historical reality which is behind a mythical story called "Heracles and Lerna's Hydra". Analysis of because this famous story is noteworthy It can provide useful insights into the origin Factual evidence of mythology, and other mechanisms of myth formation (Piccardi 2004).

Killing Hydra is the most popular myths from ancient times which is based on a natural process. Always play Many hydra heads are interpreted as follows: symbols of many water sources that feed a big swamp which is located near Lerna, and the fight between Hercules and the monster, hence, image of drainage efforts. After the last chop their hero, the hero who stayed immortal, buried it forever and put a huge and heavy stone on it in addition. Kirk (1974), initially follows the interpretation proposed by Parai Pathos and claims this instead that this myth records a fairly old politics event. In a manner similar to the killing of the Minotaur at the Knossos Palace, Hydra's killing at Lerna and related myths Nemean lion killing, all of them contain memories of old political events in addition to references to fertility rites.

Myths were also created to explain unusual landscape features and natural landmarks, inspired by mountains, cliffs and rocks that often look out of place. An example of the latter is explained by Motta & Motta, and many similar cases are known elsewhere in the world. Ancient sacred folklore has many such mythical explanations of the amazing appearance of certain natural geological formations and structures.

In recent decades, there is growing awareness among geologists, some legends and myths are based on natural phenomena, and the possibility of using an interdisciplinary approach to identify records of past geological events in a particular story.

Among the more useful uses of geological myths are the ability to add a historical record to natural disasters, which helps to avoid from danger. Some of the most damaging geophysical disasters such as earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic

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eruptions and meteorites were written in myths because of probably two mythical effects reason: first, they are very rare, and a mysterious phenomenon, and secondly, their impact on the community made them important to be remembered. Different examples of mythical explanation of such a catastrophic event can be presented in this work.

The most well-known example of volcanic eruptions can be seen in mythology of Atlantis destruction which is interpreted as broken image of super eruption of Thera volcano around 1625 BC (Friedrichetal. 2006; Manning et al. 2006). In the similar manner, the battle between giants' Olympic athletes and typhoon prisoners under Etna volcano memory of the period of intense activity of Etna and other volcanoes in the Mediterranean (Wyatt 1996; Barber & Barber 2005).

Bible examples related to earthquakes, analyzed by Bentor (1989) and Nur (1991), are: Jordan intersection and aftermath famous destruction of the wall of Jericho (Joshua 3, 4 and 6). In this situation, the site location where the incidents happened and features reported in the text, allowed the recognition in this explanation of the strong earthquake that caused collapse of the almost vertical bank of the river, across large leaf stripes Jordan Valley Fault. The likely phenomenon reoccurred in the 1546 earthquake. The water of the river is blocked and the water stopped during two days, and the of earthquakes of 1906 and 1927. Jericho's destruction was listed as follows: Seismic events in the 15th century catalog earthquake (Manetti 1457) and earthquake with the depletion of Jordan the collapse of the Wall of Jericho, which was already recognized in ancient times (Psalm 114:3-8).

Conclusion. Myth offers us amazing opportunities extracted from the historical and cultural records of unprecedented view of many regions with the effects of geological and solar system processes events of the last few thousand years.

Most of the time, the process of extracting such records from myths, natural events and processes may not be easy. It requires an application a set of geological, astronomical, archaeological and additionally cognitive tools science, history, and the humanities. We are still forced to learn lots of things about theory and methods our new field of geological mythology. Not all myths are good for such analysis, but not so much of them gives enough information which is necessary for identification the actual geological process is less specific datable occurrences such as large earthquakes and volcanoes eruptions, floods, impacts on space. Anyway, that these defined events give us opportunity to understand the geological history of the region and the actual risks posed by certain natural specific phenomenon.

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